

Insights Report

Civic Data Coop

Sept 2021 – Jan 2022

Making Public Services
People Services

CONTENTS

1. FOREWORD	3
2. INTRODUCTION	5
3. METHODOLOGY	7
4. ANALYSIS	8
5. RESULTS	9
6. INSIGHTS	10
7. OVERLAP DISCUSSION	37
8. CONCLUSION	39
9. APPENDIX.....	47

1. FOREWORD

Civic Data Coop

The vision for Civic Data Coop is to create the world's leading civic data environment, making health-related data work for the people in Liverpool City Region (LCR) while fuelling innovations of international importance. Based on a collaborative, open approach to governance the co-operative will support organisations and residents with health-related data which works for them. In turn, this will improve the lives of LCR residents while driving economic growth in health tech and digital sectors in the region.

As a multi-stakeholder organisation, the Civic Data Coop (CDC) will not only develop a new data resource, a one-of-a-kind platform, but a new type of environment with transparent governance that reflects the legal and ethical obligations to enable linkage of civic health data from multiple sources. This will give a bigger picture of health and wellbeing across LCR, while enabling citizens, preserving residents' privacy, and respecting their preferences for data uses.

Based on a collaborative, open approach the LCR Civic Data Cooperative will support people and organisations use data to:

- Translate lived experience into insight,
- Deliver innovation with impact,
- Test models for ethical, inclusive use of health data
- while preserving residents' privacy and respecting their preferences

In time CDC's vision is to create the positive changes citizens and clinicians want and the economic opportunities needed for sustainability. CDC will provide the behavioural infrastructure for people to choose to work with a common purpose to make innovation easier, within a new open, transparent, trusted environment.

Capacity

It's no secret that the public and third sectors are facing some tough internal and external challenges, and we need big ideas and brave leaders to tackle them.

That's where Capacity comes in. We provide the know-how, big-picture thinking, and hands-on time to get moving on the projects that really matter: the ones that make the biggest impact on the lives of everyday people.

In other words, you might call us a 'do-tank'. Unlike a think-tank, we also go on to do the stuff we've thought about. That means we're on the journey with the organisations we support; you won't find us producing a shiny report and leaving them to it.

We'll also get on with the job at hand (if the team wants us to), focussing less on the policies and procedures, and more on the people and real lives at the end of them. Our Northern roots stand us in good stead here; we're fiercely proud of our ability to understand our local people and places, keeping them with us along the way.

We know that in an ever-evolving digital world data will sit at the heart of our thinking and what impact we make as organisations. We are excited to work alongside CDC as real disturbers of the space, being brave, provocative and honest in order to be the leading thinkers and do-ers in this space, bringing citizens in the northwest along with their thinking and put people at the heart of the solution.

We will provide expertise where CDC want to embed service design thinking into their development; listening and discovering what is and isn't working for SMEs as part of the Design for Health Programme. This project excites us as an organisation as it speaks to our core values as do-ers as well as thinkers, helping CDC realise how they can operate to add much needed value to the system.

2. INTRODUCTION

Design Thinking for Health

As the CDC moved from idea to delivery, they commissioned Capacity to support the development of their first product- the Design Thinking for Health programme. We know innovation in health and social care is a term widely used across the Liverpool City Region, with a wealth of activity happening in the space; we also know that we are not seeing nearly enough data led innovation happening to support our public services. The aim of this programme was to better understand this noisy landscape and begin to make sense of what value CDC can add.

Working in collaboration with two concurrent workstreams focussed on brand and public involvement, The Design Thinking for Health programme set out to help CDC understand what challenges people are trying to address in the Liverpool City Region, in relation to progressing innovation of data led solutions from three key perspectives:

1. People with ideas, largely made up of SMEs
2. Organisations providing support to SMEs
3. Providers of public services

Insights were gathered to inform two key areas, firstly the shape of the programme- what do we need to do to help SMEs and public services work better together? Secondly, the broader shape of the functions of CDC- Where and how can CDC help LCR improve innovation of data led solutions for our communities? Insights were gathered from community organisations, members of the NHS, researchers, inventors, change-makers and more.

The role of CDC as an organisation relates to civic data, making best use of it and making it easier to deal with for organisations big and small. But it's hard for organisations to do that when the complexity of the public system can be extremely difficult to navigate. The ambition of the programme is to understand the different perspectives of the problems and bring people together. People who are facing operational and strategic challenges every day, who rarely get to share their 'ask' or even better a dialogue with the ideas people, people who are immersed in digital solutions and driven to get their products to market.

We know data is just one tool in getting this right, but we need to talk to the right people and ask the right questions, so we can delve into the right problems. We need to this before we can even work out what data we need.

We've got a bit of a mantra that sits at the heart of this programme:

**(Right People + Right Questions) x Right
Data
=
Product and Service design that works**

This report outlines the insights we heard and how this has shaped the next phase of thinking for the programme.

DRAFT

3. METHODOLOGY

Led by the ambition of understanding what CDC can provide to add value in this space, Capacity set out to understand the real-life experiences of SMEs, Support Organisations and influential figures in the Health and Social Care space, across the six boroughs of the Liverpool City Region (Halton, Knowsley, Liverpool, Sefton, St Helen's and Wirral).

A long list of over 75 participants were engaged including both individuals who had developed and launched products or programmes in LCR, as well as a fair representation of leaders in Local Authority or Health settings, to understand the front end and back-end barriers to idea adoption and support for SMEs. The ambition of this rapid research phase was to challenge our assumptions and understand what the programme needs to deliver for all stakeholders. Supporting these insights is a plethora of existing collateral and local research, for example work led by The Innovation Agency.

DRAFT

4. ANALYSIS

Insights were analysed using a deductive coding method. This means that a “codebook” was developed in advance and the interview analysers used this as a reference to look for themes in the conversations. The codebook was taken from the P.O.I.N.T.S analysis method.

P.O.I.N.T.S stands for problems, opportunities, insights, needs, themes and system challenges.

Problems refer to the challenges people are facing at any level, whether through an existing support programme or as a local authority.

Opportunities relate to aspects of the current system or community that are either working brilliantly or would be brilliant with some extra development, or actions that could remove a problem or meet a need.

Insights are contextual comments, unique to that individual, given by the individual.

Needs develop in response to gaps or where support is unmet.

Themes are current thoughts and comments repeated across the community.

Finally, **System Challenges** are barriers affecting how this community access support, share need and collaborate. This stems from wider systems such as health, social work, commissioning, funding etc.

For each of these codes, quotes given directly by the participant were noted, as well as implied or evident trends eked out by the analyser, were noted.

Over the course of these interviews Capacity had regular touch points with Civic Data Coop to steer the design of the programme and respond to some of the headline messages heard from the participants. These touch points have helped to shape the design and narrative of the programme.

5. RESULTS

Over the course of the engagement piece, 75 interviews were held in total. Interviews took place between September and early December 2021. The majority of interviews were conducted online or over the telephone.

19 (25%) of these conversations were with participants who work for a local authority or health & social care providers, 30 (40%) were with participants who represented a support organisation, however many of these conversations also give insight into the experience for SME's. Finally, 26 (35%) of interviews were with SME's or individuals who are working in this space.

In the following sections, we have summarised the insights gained by each category and included a section summarising point of contrast and overlap between the interviewee's experiences.

DRAFT

6. INSIGHTS

6.1 Health and Social Care Providers

6.1.1 Problems

When speaking to public sector leaders we heard problems that typically fall into three buckets:

- a. Service delivery: Problems our residents face that require solutions and we have a responsibility to shape and deliver
- b. Internal challenges: Internal to the public sector agency
- c. SME engagement: Problems we have engaging with SMEs

The problems we heard from LCR health and social care providers were vast, each provider presenting a number of ongoing, complex problems. It's clear there are a plethora of pressure points for councils, trusts and general practice, with little understanding of how to start unpicking and solving these issues. The loudest insights are summarised below:

a. Service Delivery

We heard that the cost of **Looked After Children is a growing problem**, with cases and resulting costs increasing year on year. A problem that is multi-generational, with a pattern appearing of one-third of children already in care, seeing their own children going into care later in life. Local Authorities shared their concern about the rising cost and poor outcomes for the provision currently in place alongside the concern that we are not reaching families when they first begin to struggle and instead intervene at crisis point.

Alongside this, there was discussion around the growing demand in Children's services. For example, we heard that it is difficult to **identify the right families to work with in Early Help**, enabling more families to manage independently, giving more time to finding the families who struggle on un-noticed. We heard there is a "chasm of support difference between children and adults help", particularly around **SEN and children with disabilities**, with a need to get families better engaged with

the Education, Care and Health planning (ECHP) process, and embed a social model of disability within communities, for a stronger support network.

It is felt that there could be a move towards a more progressive, supportive story-lead method of capturing evidence for programmes such as Child Protection, where currently **meetings can feel threatening and a way of capturing problems, rather than progress.**

“We would love the facility for parents to collect evidence of their own progress, so this can be presented better to Child Protection. These meetings are high anxiety given the subject, dominated by professionals documented by what parents have not done... we’d love to see a better approach to this.” - Asst Director of Children’s Services, Local Authority

We heard the **behaviour in Social Care is around reducing risk and referring to services to evidence ‘help’**, this feeds into the problem of services not being tailored enough to the individual, resulting in poor outcomes, adding to increasing waiting lists in a ‘prescribed help’ approach.

Public Health leaders told us that the region struggle with **poor educational outcomes**, with schools feeling un-supported by communities, where intergenerational experience of education is poor, resulting in a lack of value and decline in respect for the educational system.

Local authority leaders want to increase the attention we put on our **environments**, we see energy and solutions being generated in tech and lifestyle choices, and not on the role of clean and maintained environments that actually have a bigger contribution to health. Included in this is the **poor housing stock** existing in the region, we have over-crowded, space-poor stock and properties falling into disrepair and still lived in, having a direct effect on the health and wellbeing of the inhabitants.

Linked to this we heard about the **increase in children presenting at A&E with asthma exacerbations**, which can be linked directly to poor environments suffering with air quality conditions, and damp housing. There is an appetite to embed a preventative approach to this problem through a number of avenues, such as medication management, highways pilots that can reduce traffic at schools at peak times and the integration of community nursing and housing providers to work to identify and tackle damp and ventilation in the home.

Public sector leaders spoke of how we **need to achieve co-production in statutory services**. An example shared was in a Domestic Violence (DV) service, where there have been disconnects between person centred assessments followed by fixed offers of support with no flexibility to their need or aspirations. This often leads to poor engagement with support that is offered and a rabbit wheel situation occurs, where the individual is seen as 'un-committed to recovery'.

b. Internal System Challenges

Health and social care providers spoke in depth about the common problems they face both internally within their employing agency and also working with and through other public services.

Councils spoke of **low workplace wellbeing** and burn out, especially at a time of pressure. The organisations are big and its challenging to affect organisational wide change.

"We've seen lots of input and resilience workshops take place for our staff, but things are not changing within our teams. The culture needs nudging in the right direction, so we can imbed change better" - Local Authority Senior Leader

We heard that between internal departments **sharing of intelligence between teams is poor**, which means budgeting and service development is not driving decisions and shaping strategy. Local authorities are aware of the need to digitise and use data better, but they do not have the internal resource to consider this fully and implement intelligent frameworks across complex, disjointed teams. Many interviewees spoke of a **need to educate teams on the use of data**, especially where **governance can be a roadblock** to progress. Some of the more 'tech facing' departments were excited about a national upgrade from analogue to digital, but they didn't feel supported by the leadership teams to deliver their ambition. Local authorities honestly shared their anxiety and concern about **not being digitally enabled**, feeling that digitally led initiatives are tinkering around the edges working with colleagues who are not confidently able to have impact led conversations, **we're overlooking some of the fundamental building blocks needed to run in the digital world**.

"Systematically, we are trying to go from the penny farthing to the flying skateboard" - Local Authority Digital Lead

Looking ahead and horizon scanning came through as an area councils feel like they could improve. Teams **have limited resources and are stuck firefighting problems**,

this can be a disabler to accelerating change for the future. To support this, senior leaders **want a clearer path to plan well for future provision** supported by clearer modelling to **demonstrate how change now can create opportunities to save costs** over a longer period of time, understanding impact just isn't on anyone's busy agenda. This can be particularly difficult when implementing change across different teams, where the budgets are separate and teams want to hold onto control and their pressured budgets.

“We find it hard to articulate how changes to the system avoid spending further down the line, particularly if it doesn't have an immediate knock on effect on the same service. No one is doing this well, so it continues to be hard to invest in prevention.” - Senior Local Authority Leader

Local Authorities have advanced and adapted their ways of working in a way they never expected to over the past 18 months. Despite this magnitude of change they recognise the opportunities offered by digital tools and approaches to target and deliver services better and save money are not being maximised. They take part in pilots and begin to draft strategies but translating this into operations remains a significant challenge and they are fearful they will be left behind. This is an anxiety against the backdrop of the 'day job' framed by decreasing budgets and increasing demand. Local Authorities want help to focus their thinking and support to be digitally enabled.

c. SME Engagement

It commonly came through that **SME's developing solutions in this space are attempting to steer the resolutions to problems** that are not perceived as 'real' or important enough for providers to allocate resource to develop and nurture. This can present when SME's have already jumped through several hoops to develop their offering, so the solution becomes niche and not adaptable to real life.

“The bang for the buck [for SME tech solutions], is often not what is promised, either because it doesn't speak to a wider population or because we need to talk about tech at a wider population health level, rather than particular chronic conditions” - Asst Director of Adults Services, Local Authority

There is a perception from councils and health professionals that SME **ideas stay in the theory space for too long**, making it difficult to synchronise up fast paced responses to problems if the organisation needs further support to tailor and develop the idea to real life, something that providers cannot accommodate amongst the other noise of their work. This idea-vacuum can drain the momentum out of solutions, widening the **gap between solution thinking and application**.

Reflecting further on this, Providers spoke about **needing SME's to also support with the 'doing' and 'application' of digital solutions**, who they assume have the capacity to digest the intelligence found within the data, understand the themes and drive forwards the use of data as an enabler of change.

6.1.2 Opportunities

Opportunities, in our analysis, refers to where better outcomes could be the result of an action or change in parts of the system that are already in existence or where we could be doing more of the same.

For instance, there are **various programmes of support being delivered across the region with the focus on innovation in the public space**, many of which we will capture in the following section for SME Support Organisations. With further understanding of where these programmes are not meeting the ambition for SME's we can start to understand better the opportunities for Civic Data Coop to learn from this in their delivery of their product launch and help to involve support programmes in the conversation to continually review and improve their offering.

During the conversations with leaders in Public Health, opportunities were discussed around the need for community engagement and empowerment in order to really excel at solutions to many of the problems faced by citizens in LCR. **There is a disparity of community groups across the city**, with more community organisations established in the more affluent south of Liverpool, and less activity in more deprived areas in the Liverpool borough. This is likely to be reflected in boroughs across the region, where the offering of community support is weighted in favour of the affluent areas.

As less and less money is pumped into the budgets of Public Health spending, it is becoming more important to empower citizens to engage with the system and be motivated to create positive change within their own communities. The focus here from a provider perspective, is that money can then stay in the system to support those who are suffering the most. The opportunity presented here is for **SMEs to help engage with data and citizens to really un-pick neighbourhood problems so that communities can come together and find solutions to the less complex problems**. By empowering communities to have better self-care, social care can then have more time to help those with the highest level of need.

We heard that there are departments within local authorities that are **storing lots of intelligence from residents, but this is not getting shared across teams** to give support systems a head start in identifying those at risk of falling into crisis, for example when we see that those early indicators are being missed repeatedly.

“We know that missed council tax payments amongst other things are indicators of families needing more support, but there is no sharing of intelligence through to Early Help. This principle could be broadened out beyond the Local Authority into the private sector, such as United Utilities, British Gas etc” - Senior Local Authority Leader

Councils are aware of the **need to move from a traditionally analogue service into the digital space in the near future and parts of the system are hungry for change.** Improved tech such as sensors at home will not only put residents at the centre of demand and response but will also help local authorities to save money over time by intervening earlier, managing conditions better and transforming the ways the leadership teams think about commissioning, problem diagnosis and response and improve the internal connections across departments.

“One of the problems we face is that we have very little API software, no system speaks directly to another system, anything to do with matching up [poor quality data] is very time consuming and takes away from the service delivery. We have a vision of what we want the service to look like, but we struggle to keep this on the strategy agenda with the senior leadership teams in the council.” - Telecare Service manager, Local Authority

By shining a light on the potential for improvement in this space, providers such as housing associations know that SME’s can start to play a vital role in the shaping of our systems, attracting talent into the conversation and spitting out a more person centred, wrap around, responsive service for citizens.

“There is so much opportunity for SMEs to play a role in helping to deliver services that are always overstretched... There is a big appetite for more tele-health solutions, but all stakeholders need to come along on the journey.” - Housing Association Snr Leader

Of course, there is also a lot of thinking going into this landscape centrally. The inception of System P, via MerseyCare will help to draw analysis from CIPHA – an integrated NHS, local authority and public health record, to align intelligence for all service delivery users to access.

The CDC will support local leaders use this intelligence to focus on what innovative digital tools can empower their teams to understand population needs and trends, identify system pressures and opportunities and measure the impact of their work, ultimately meaning citizens can lead healthier, more connected and independent lives.

6.1.3 Insights

During our analysis, we gathered a number of points raised by participants that felt they were specifically affected their part of the system. We have grouped these points under “insights”.

Some providers described their experience of innovation being driven by academia, with activity being stuck in thinking and discussion mode for too long. This repeated pattern of **‘words not turning into action’**, has potentially made the distance between providers and SME’s wider over time. Providers spoke about **solutions being ‘over egged’**, where previously adopted solutions promise a lot, but under deliver in application.

“Tech is really big, but often over egged in the Adult Social Care world... we need SMEs to not over promise. We must find some consistency for where tech can play a part. It's currently a minor consideration and often in contracts or specifications it's just a throw away comment. Where are the opportunities that are missed?” - Local Authority Snr Leader

As we highlighted in the ‘Opportunities’ above, we understand that Public Services continue to be cash poor, so we know that **the money needs to stay with those hardest hit**. This strengthens the message that we heard from councils that **solutions to problems are often not addressing the most pressing issues that we know our communities are facing**, so don’t make it past the first hurdle when pitching a new idea.

Hearing this it’s clear that the **relationship between SMEs and Providers needs to be improved**. If SMEs were equipped with better evidence of problems and real insight from the people doing the work and absorbing the system pressures, more person-centred solutions could be spat out as a result. If Providers trusted SMEs to unpick the real knotty problems in their digital innovation space, and helped them to understand how the system works, then SMEs would start with solid foundations for an idea. If these sides could work together more harmoniously, better solutions to real problems would inevitably happen.

6.1.4 Needs

For our analysis, needs refer to parts of the system that currently don’t exist but would help providers to meet the needs of people sooner, support citizens better and create more opportunity for innovation and talent to stay in the region.

Providers spoke about pressures in Early Help frequently throughout our interview process, and the **need to create ways to better evidence family progress to feed into the decision making by the people involved**, particularly around a more flexible way of recording the ambition from parents to make positive changes, tackling the current system that can feel like it is set up to record failures as a priority. This need

is fed into by the insight mentioned prior to this section about how communities can play a significant role in the solutions.

This 're-modelling' of thinking also came through when talking about mental and physical disabilities, where a social approach to disability would help empower those with these conditions to excel in society, rather than the current pattern of seeing citizens with disabilities lead more complex, disadvantaged and ultimately shorter lives.

A social approach to dealing with the problems laid out in the earlier section ties together the many disparate problems and opportunities across the LCR. With the **increasing need for people to be more empowered to look after themselves well, there is a greater need for neighbourhood mobilisation.** These solutions must be accessible to those hardest hit, and community generated and run to deliver the most impactful solution. This also bleeds into the need for some schools to receive more community focused support, where we also heard that some teaching in schools and support for teachers is poor.

Health and social care providers feel they not equipped to mobilise the community involvement aspect to these solutions, so need new thinking and investment in this space, a great open door for SMEs, but they must consider that results need to be far reaching and cost effective to be adopted. The **citizens need to be listened to and given a role to play in the creation and execution of solutions** to ensure they are designed for the people at every point of contact with providers.

Participants mentioned the **need to develop a model that could help councils talk confidently about the impact changes are having, in order to capture the value of change and see how this can seep out across departments or teams, creating positive change and saving costs over time,** especially where budgets are not aligned and progress in one team may have a knock-on positive effect down the line for an entirely separate department. Financial planning is currently siloed into individual teams, and it is hard for leaders to make informed decisions where there is little to no intelligent financial modelling at top level.

Finally, interviewees spoke about the general public and their relationship with data. As digital citizen services have become the new imperative for government, data is the key to improving the way government organisations operate and deliver for their citizens, and a bright light has been shone on this during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Citizen data presents enormous potential value to consumers, businesses and public authorities. In the digital age, a range of information about citizens can now be used far more easily for a wider set of purposes, and for purposes which were not initially anticipated. These can also involve malicious intent and, without careful

management, harm to individuals, society and national security. There is a need for a civic educational piece around the use of data.

“We need to be more people focused, rather than data focused” - Asst Director of Adults Services, Local Authority

Alongside improved use of data, **members of the public need to be an active and engaged part of the UK’s data system.** Providers should listen and respond to concerns, but also be empowered to use data and be willing to lead, educate and persuade where there is strong evidence in support of interventions. If a larger proportion of the public feel confident in our data system, more may engage with it in an informed way and access its benefits. Risks in the public space need careful managing, and not all citizens will value economic gains equally, but an inability to harness data in a comprehensive way can, for instance, mean missed opportunities to help vulnerable families or improve public health.

“We know that there is work to be done on the public perception of data, we cannot do this alone. Without the support of the public, we know we won’t be able to do our best pro-active and preventative work.... People need to engage and be comfortable with the ethics.” - Innovation Lead, Health Trust

6.1.5 Themes

In our analysis ‘themes’ are thoughts and comments that were repeated across the Provider community. In this section we have centred this thinking around the role of the Civic Data Cooperative. During the conversations many providers were excited about the idea of the CDC, most had heard about the organisation’s establishment, and we saw that providers had started to expect various different outputs or deliverables from the organisation, as it matured.

We heard participants talk about the fragmented systems across public services, how **the majority of work is siloed , making it difficult for providers to have a live overview of a person or a community where systems don’t talk to each other, and teams are busy firefighting problems**, meaning that communication and horizon scanning isn’t happening. There was an expectation from some of the interviewees that Civic Data Coop would be able to knit these systems together to create a clearer picture of a resident and ultimately support the vision for a more ‘person centred, wrap around care’ approach.

This was reflected upon by interviewees who worked for providers through the COVID-19 pandemic, a time where health data has been shared with local authorities and housing associations in new ways. For example, local authorities have received

access to the NHS shielding patients database, allowing authorities to better target support, including food parcels and pharmacy deliveries, to vulnerable individuals. But there is still a long way to go in this space and many felt that **we continue to see social care get left behind in the innovation space**, with health always tending to lead the market for innovation and investment. For there to be meaningful change for citizens, Social Care has to be given the same opportunity for innovation.

“Over the years we see money be poured into health services, but without proper investment, we will continue to cut spending in social care which lacks innovation and improvement. There are less commercial operations in social care, but we must find ways to make this more attractive to SMEs. No progress here has a direct impact on our residents.” - Speciality Research Lead and Mental Health Nurse

One of the barriers to providers making progress independently in this space is a **lack of understanding of the correct protocols around data governance** and many participants hoped that the establishment of CDC would lead to solutions in this space. It was acknowledged by most that in order to have sustainable adoption, the governance of new technologies needs to be informed by engagement with local citizens to ensure that it is trustworthy.

Leading figures in the provider space frequently referred to **tele-health and sensor technology as the future of innovation and planning of public services**. There is an appetite for this to be adopted quickly but a lack of direction and leadership within the space means that progression is slow. Leaders are hungry for some direction and support and there were echoes of expectation for CDC to support in this space.

6.1.6 System Challenges

Finally, **System Challenges** in this section are risks to bear in mind when considering future solutions in the space. Some barriers can affect how this network of providers currently support their clients or staff, share need and collaborate across the landscape. This stems from wider systems such as health, social work, commissioning, funding etc.

Internally, interviewees acknowledged that **there is work to be done within the culture of local authorities**, who can often take an outdated approach to tackling problems. A tangible example of this comes to the surface when speaking about the switch from analogue to digital systems and the paralysis that councils face when moving forwards in this space. The current teams are not equipped with the right tools to think about digitising complex and fragmented systems, and do not know where to start when considering any longer-term change to data and technology internally. **Before considering solutions, first we need to be confident that the internal culture is ready to adopt new ways of thinking** and equipped or supported to carry out change.

“The problem we have at the moment is that tech assumes we are already managing the tele-health care space, but the whole system behind telehealth, making the data useful and responsive, just doesn't exist... our teams are not empowered to understand or make sense of this.” - Local Authority Snr Leader

We also heard that **risk aversion can be a barrier to change**. Whether this takes the shape of risk management between client cases, where a lot of time is spent on choosing the pathway with the lowest risk stratification, or whether it means taking risks over big decisions that could offer digital streamlining to systems and solutions. Here it is worth noting that the language of risk in this context also referred to data governance and the fear of making mistakes with client or citizen data that could lead to reputational damage for organisations or local authorities.

“We struggle to get internal departments to speak to each other. There is so much intel wrapped up in siloed teams, but everyone is scared of data protection. I don't understand how this is still a barrier in our own organisation” - Local Authority Snr Leader

All participants nodded to the fact that **we need do-ers to take the digital space forwards with the involvement of people on the ground and members of the public at the heart of the solutions**. Currently when innovation is discussed internally ideas and application are a long way from each other and with staff siloed into their departments, progress isn't made. This outdated approach means that no advancements in understanding un-met need are made and providers continue to help those with high need, or at crisis instead of spending more time preventing crisis, and helping people stay independent and healthy for longer.

“The wisdom of our internal workforce is much greater than we recognise. We need to start harnessing this potential, so our people have a licence to innovate. They need to know where to go when they have an idea and that they'll be listened to. If we could have the tools and capability to engage and empower our staff quickly and cheaply, we'd be doing less of the work, but achieving much more.” - Local Authority Snr Leader

Externally to the system, barriers were discussed around **public digital access and literacy**, with the example given that around 20% of people in the region not being able to upload COVID test results online for one of these two reasons. We know this

digital inequity across LCR needs to be kept at the front of our minds when thinking about solution generation.

Liverpool has high ranking academic institutions, with over 70,000 students choosing to study here each year. The city has some of the top-ranking universities in the world for research and development and we know we are producing high quality graduates from the choice of three recognised universities, and an endless choice of higher education offerings across the region. However, we also know that **the city region suffers from 'brain-drain' with many highly qualified alumni choosing to leave the city** to develop their ideas or businesses elsewhere.

"Our universities produce outstanding graduates, but an inadequate number of high-quality jobs and high barriers to entry for entrepreneurship means the region experiences high levels of 'brain drain'." - SME Support Organisation

The organisations interviewed were of the opinion that part of this departure is due to a **poor offering of high-quality jobs in the region**. This is a problem that the Combined Authority is aware of and is trying to remedy through various touch points with the system, where we have seen an increase in support organisations that offer a helping hand to talented people in the region to develop their business locally.

We have the potential to harness this talent better in order to drive economic growth in the region, capturing the ideas at seed level to nurture and springboard university alumni and other budding entrepreneurs to support our service providers in finding innovative solutions to complex problems.

6.2 Support Organisations

Alongside the conversations we had with Health and Social Care providers, we also spoke to a number of organisations who currently offer support programmes for small-medium enterprises in the city region to find out what their understanding of this space is, what works well, what doesn't work so well and what do they feel SMEs need less or more of to be able to succeed better, faster.

Support in this space can represent anything from advice on or enablement of new technologies, to up to 12 months advice and funding to get business in their infancy off the ground through various offerings of business support packages and programmes.

We spoke to 30 members of supportive organisations from programmes hosted by the following organisations and projects:

- Alder Hey
- Innovation Agency
- Liverpool Health Partners
- Wellcome Trust
- Growth Platform
- Kindred
- Health Matters
- Real World Validation
- Liverpool 5G Create
- We Are Nova

6.2.1 Problems

There are multiple streams of support that we know are available for SMEs to tap into across the city region, aimed at meeting the needs of a business in all sectors, with many focusing on innovation. These organisations provide anything from seed funding to financial or business planning advice, which is why we are referring to them as ‘SME Support Organisations’. The problems outlined below are a mix of insights gathered from across these organisations and also the SMEs and entrepreneurs who have received support through the various support streams.

We heard from within this community, especially in reference to SMEs developing in the Health and Social Care space, was that **this landscape is highly complex and difficult to navigate**. Parts of the system that many assume talk to each other, don't. With each trust, general practice and authority operating via their own system, **citizen records do not match up across the whole landscape**. This makes it difficult for organisations supporting in this space to give consistent advice, slowing down the process of SMEs getting a product to market as many barriers stand in the way.

“We know there is a challenge with the linking of data stored in health systems. We need to be thinking about unique identifies to move this thinking forwards... the work is only just starting” - SME Data org

“Our biggest challenge is access to public health data, data architecture and expertise in creating an arc around the data in order to validate our work.” -SME Telehealth org

Teams sitting within the NHS and councils are also fragmented, so getting to the right person, within the right team can be time consuming and frustrating for SMEs trying to navigate the space and move an idea through the system.

“We have world leading health and academic institutions, but networks and funding streams are fragmented” - SME Support org

“It is so often the case that the procurement people are so far removed from the clinical side of things that they don’t truly understand the value of the solution you are bringing to the table.” - SME Health org

Organisations are aware that there is a vast number of support programmes and initiatives to get ideas and new businesses off the ground, sometimes an overwhelming choice that can be paralysing to new SMEs. However, it was mentioned more than once that the **delivery of these initiatives varies in quality**, and that in many cases there is a **shortage in capacity or capability to provide constructive advice to overcome barriers**. This issue repeats itself as there is a void where there should be better programme evaluation, understanding of timeline and improved product development.

“We needed more facilitated introductions to people who have the problems we knew existed. Their people are traditionally hard to access and are usually so immersed in their day job that the people who can potentially solve their problems never get to meet them.” - SME HealthTech

The supporting organisations also spoke about **the challenges of advising SMEs when they are distinct stages of maturity**. Interviewees mentioned that sometimes the pre-designed support doesn’t reflect a specific stage in the development of an idea or business plan. SMEs that access support through the existing programmes in the regions vary in size, profit, maturity and expertise and there we heard both SMEs and the supporting organisations talk about how a **direct contact with a mentor, or an understanding of who the SME should go to for advice at what stage within the system could help speed up progress**.

“There is almost too much support on offer in LCR and it’s very difficult to navigate and be certain that you’re doing the right thing... An ideal business support programme would give high-level business expertise and experience-based help and advice from people who already have the scars from trying and failing.” SME, HealthTech

This fractured map is also mimicked when organisations spoke about the funding available for SMEs to bid into.

“The NHS doesn’t like to be sold to, it’s hard to understand the procurement frameworks, instead we need to build relationships” - SME Support Org

Some participants were frustrated by the motivation behind provider innovation. There was a feeling that innovation is being driven only by policy and a ‘we have to do this’ attitude, rather than the desire to improve services in the eye of the citizen. Organisations recognised that the **solutions to problems could be more people focused, rather than policy driven**, and that the provider system doesn’t value this approach enough. Here we have the opportunity to engage better with our citizens to help them to drive the change we need to see in the region, to be part of the solution.

“Innovation is policy driven – this isn't real. We need innovation to be at citizen level. We need to twine policy and citizens together and then leverage innovators to co-create the solution.” - Researcher, University

6.2.2 Opportunities

In our research phase, as we spoke to the SME community and the supporting programme leaders, we heard about the events and hackathons that crop up in the region, which are designed to bring groups of people and organisations together to collaboratively develop a solutions and build networks in the community.

It quickly became a trend that SMEs shared ‘hackathon’ exhaustion and that behind this was the thinking that traditionally **hackathons don’t support unique, individual ideas with directional advice, instead these events can feel like a way for SMEs to pool their ideas into a space full of risk**, where ideas can be shared with competitors. There was a real appetite to change this event delivery model for something more meaningful, bringing together the right people, but delivering a more robust method to allow SMEs to improve their networks and develop their ideas.

“Liverpool [City Region] is not Silicon Valley and has a very immature tech ecosystem. One size does not fit all, and it is competitive out there, this needs to be considered in the hackathon approach.” - SME

With new support programmes and streams of funding popping up regularly, giving SMEs an opportunity to develop their ideas, the region has the potential to provide real wrap around structure to businesses with a range of needs in the various sticky growth phases small to medium sized businesses experience.

Below is a non-exhaustive map of the current support packages available to the SME community in the region.

Organisation	Support
VEC	LCR 4 START
	LCR 4.0
	LCR Holistic
ORCA	Digital Health Academy
	Market Intelligence
	Compliance
Glow	Mobile app developer in Healthcare, HealthTech and MedTech.
Growth Platform	Be the business
	Business Resilience
	Enterprise Hub
	Flexible Growth Fund
	Future Innovation Fund
	Gather (Digital Creative Tech Sector)
	Sustain
	Help to Grow
	Innovate UK EDGE
	Finance Hub
	NatWest Accelerator
	Sensor City
	Shift
	High Growth Programme
	Business Growth Programme
Kindred	Investment and peer-support for Ventures or Projects delivered by social purpose organisations
MTC	Digital Manufacturing Accelerator
Innovation Agency	Health Matters (in partnership with the Growth Platform)
Daresbury	Digital Tech Cluster
Liverpool Ventures	Investment and business support for early-stage ideas initially within health and social care
Form	Leadership and organisational development support for established organisations
We are Nova	Tech start-up programme
	Stage founders
	Mentoring
E-health Cluster	Support collaboration between technology and care organisations.
Welcome Trust	Faculty of Health & Life Sciences at the University, programme to support academic entrepreneurs

Kindred	Investment and peer-support for Ventures or Projects delivered by social purpose organisations
Alder Hey	Innovation Hub with product development and testing capability across Digital and MedTech.

6.2.3 Insights

There were several unique comments made in reference to how SMEs could have improved influence or access to health and social care products and solutions made by the participants of our research phase.

Navigating the funding can also be complex and some of the participants we engaged with felt that **funding repeatedly falls into the hands of academics who know the space well already, whereas SMEs at an earlier stage of development can find the funding space intimidating**. This speaks to the problem raised by providers when discussing the lack of engagement with SMEs, where councils and health professionals spoke about ideas staying in the theory space for too long, and a shortage of ‘do-ers’ to accompany the ‘thinkers’.

Organisations mentioned that when ideas make it to the procurement stage, we see that the **slickest and well packaged ideas find it easier to win backing from commissioners, rather than the ideas that tackle more complex or knotty problems**, if their branding and presentation isn’t as well preened as their competitors.

This procurement problem is exacerbated due to **Commissioners comfortably commissioning providers with track record, rather than new providers looking to cut their teeth with their innovations**, meaning that the same external providers are awarded contracts, where new business struggle to be seen and heard.

Organisations spoke about SMEs not understanding or valuing the importance of Research and Development as part of the journey and that their idea needed to be tested. We heard that is it **commonplace for SMEs to jump straight into the solution generation, without thoroughly investigating the problem, and informing their design with thorough research and development**. Conversely, we also heard from the SME community that there is a lack of investment in Research and Development meaning barriers can be put in the way of market access when time is wasted in the effort to generate this independently.

There was a real, tangible appetite here for a data sharing platform in the region, with suggestions this should also include data captured by VCSEs. Some hoped that CDC might be the solution to bringing together all this messy data into one place, to create a trustworthy research environment, to support not only research and

developments, but to ultimately help to build policy from an innovation level upwards.

6.2.4 Needs

Similarly to the previous insights discussed around difficulties pitching to procurement and commissioning, we know that these supporting organisations and the programmes they **offer need to have a stronger influence on the commissioning model with health and social care**, in order to support SMEs getting a foot in the door with their product. This **significant need for behavioural change within the system is necessary if we want to promote the adoption of ideas**, and help Providers be ambassadors for promoting new ways of working, freeing them up from traditional ways of working.

Interviewees told us that most ideas are flowing into the health space, as it is seen as more lucrative, and presenting 'solutions' are often niche to a specific problem. These participants went on to tell us that ideas are flowing into social care and mental health present less frequently. Therefore, **social care and mental health needs to be made more attractive to SMEs in order to attract talent and new thinking to the space**.

In order to get the SME marketplace and public services collaborating more effectively there also **needs to be some steer from leaders in the public sector space, and a place for these needs to be explored and presented to SMEs**. In this manner a culture of horizon scanning can evolve, based on the strategic aims of the sector leaders.

Once an idea is adopted into these supporting programmes for development, the idea needs to be tested. **When things aren't working the organisation needs to be empowered to pivot quickly and recover from setbacks**; we heard that the programmes are not always equipped to offer this to ideas at varying stages of maturity. Participants reflected here on the **role that CDC could play in the testing of these ideas**, asking if they could offer a place for SMEs to access data to trial and validate ideas, making the offering more robust to present to the sector.

Ideas at all levels of maturity need to be supported through these programmes, no mean feat when the organisations structure, cash flow and resource will be different in each case.

6.3.5 Themes

In our analysis we have pulled together some emerging themes that were repeated by various interviewees who represented the supporting organisation community. These themes pierced through the conversations gave us a flavour for what this community feels about the current landscape, and what the future solutions should be.

We heard repeatedly that the **NHS needs to nurture better relationships, to avoid being sold to**. If health is able to include SMEs in the discussion about innovation and deployment, then SME's would feel more supported and included in the conversation and deliver better solutions, with the help of mentors and close contacts within a health environment. If these relationships could be cultivated, it would generate a more conducive pathway to progress, where SMEs would have a better understanding of the context of pressing problems that service providers face, rather than trying to cut through the noise with niche solutions to non-urgent issues, that providers don't see as a valuable use of time. **If service providers could present the most urgent problems to businesses, then SMEs would be more prepared to un-pick and support with ideas** that could be carried through to delivery.

"It feels like there are lots of health tech start-ups, but very few are addressing the real problems in communities." - SME

Small businesses find it difficult to navigate the NHS, where **the system and funding streams are complex**. This coupled with the above, where businesses find it difficult to have conversations and get real support from the clinicians or procurement, legal and financial experts result in the landscape feeling intimidating or hostile for people who are not already based within it.

"It is virtually impossible to engage with the right people in the NHS. Introductions need to be with the right people, if they are going to happen at all." - SME

The community also spoke about how many of the **schemes available in LCR are set up to support and invest in business when they are in their growth stage, rather than when an idea is in infancy**; resulting in smaller businesses with less robust ideas struggling to find the support to overcome barriers alone.

The focus of the conversation circling around to health also drew out in our analysis that **social care and mental health continue to be left out of the conversation, and therefore will continue to see less innovation led conversation in their areas**,

without more established routes and open conversations including SMEs into these services.

When considering how the Civic Data Coop would complement this space where SMEs come for support in their development and testing, these **organisations wanted CDC to be a database for relevant data sets that could help to validate or help ideas to fail faster, to speed up development from conception to pitch.** Organisations spoke about SMEs not having enough access or expertise to draw out the intelligence sitting with health and social care systems to prove the need for their bespoke solution.

“SMEs think they are evidence based but it’s actually the concept that has an evidence base. We need to unpick this better for our businesses.” - Senior Researcher, University

Ultimately, these themes reflect on empowering the SMEs to have better, more insightful conversations and support with experts within in their destination area, to give a more stable pathway to generating solutions. Access to the datasets to help to test and make solutions more robust would help businesses to be more confident in their ideas before they are ready to pitch their product to procurement teams.

6.2.6 System Challenges

Throughout the public service system in LCR we can see there are various barriers to how SMEs are not only able to access support, but also work effectively within the public service environment to create real change and offer new products and resolutions.

Throughout the public service structures, we hear that the **internal communities are risk averse** and struggle to take the leap to find innovative products and ways of working. Adoption is slow and as the providers recognise from the earlier section of this report, the internal culture makes it difficult to adopt new methods, and execution is key; the system needs ‘do-ers’ as well as ‘thinkers’.

Local authorities specifically are overworked, have little to no time to horizon scan and ever tightening budgets to plan and innovate, so risk is a real barrier for SMEs to enter this space.

Zooming out from individual teams we also heard that **governance synergy across public services is near impossible, with siloed teams each having their own data governance policy and little confidence to explore new ways of working across services** without experts in this space. We know that public services can lack

confidence in the accuracy, consistency and duplication of their data, and often don't have the tools to uncover hidden data or analyse the information in useful ways, creating conflicting data flows and lack of trust in the information.

Organisations also raised concerns about the movement to deliver support online via tele-health or similar embraces of virtual assistance but recognised that this pulls away from the messaging that conversations need to be happening across communities, delivering inclusive, wrap around solutions; a challenge when **some communities are not tech-ready and disengage with online services**.

Most importantly, we continued to hear that for SMEs to be most successful in creating products for public services, they **need to have a deeper understanding of the providers most urgent needs**. Organisations repeatedly see businesses create viable products but getting nowhere because the system doesn't see the problem as a big enough issue to divert resource and money into a solution.

6.3 Small-Medium Sized Enterprises

Finally, we also engaged with LCR based small-medium sized enterprises as part of our research to understand from their perspective what navigating this landscape felt like from a variety of different product development scenarios. We wanted to understand from them what the good and not so good things about developing a product in LCR felt like. Again, we used the P.O.I.N.T.S analysis method to pull out our findings to inform this report.

6.3.1 Problems

We heard various SMEs talk about issues around accessing financial support dependent on the maturity of their idea or product. Some interviewees reflected on the early development of their ideas, sharing that **seed funding is difficult to access, so there is pressure to self-fund ideas, which is hard for individuals with no business backing or experience**. This could be a big barrier to lots of entrepreneurs acting on brilliant ideas that don't materialise into real innovation.

Others spoke about there not being cash available for businesses to develop pre revenue, adding to the pressure for new SMEs to self-fund. Some also found that in order to trade it is expected that there need to be established trading account held by the SME, or be start-up, and their idea fell through the gap when trying to access support. These interviewees also shared that they felt their ideas could have moved

faster through the development stage if there was better access to data in the system to evidence their designs.

“At the beginning of our journey we found it impossible to find the right support for us, there was a lot out there, but we just fell through the gaps some support was only contingent on having 12 months trading history, or a full set of accounts, other support was reserved solely for start-ups” - SME

When speaking about using data as part of solutions there were some conflicting points raised in terms of application and what is available out there for SMEs to access at early maturity stage. Interviewees spoke of there being **little to no access to data, especially to GP info and patient data**, however this request didn't seem to be founded on the knowledge of information that GPs actually hold on patients. Others spoke about **not feeling empowered to understand, analyse and use data to their full advantage**, something they felt they couldn't get from the support programmes they had signed up to.

Interviewees had a spectrum of opinions on the available support within Liverpool City Region. It was apparent that depending on the stage of development the SMEs or their idea was, there were differences in perspectives on what help was available and relevant to their situation. Some reflected that there is **no clear place for SMEs to find support, and that knowing where to start is difficult, whereas others spoke about the overwhelming choice engineering confusion and paralysis**, creating a stagnant pool of SMEs unsure which option will support them best.

These problems centring around finance, data access and maturity prove that there needs to be a better model for SMEs to be able to choose which support programme is the right one for them, depending on the status of their business, the evidence they need and the maturity of their finance and strategy.

6.3.2 Opportunities

Despite this there was positive feedback on some of the support that participants received from various schemes. The feedback here was that the support given was of a really high standard, but the only downside was how much time it took to find the right sort of support for their specific idea.

“The quality of the support was really good, but I did have to spend a long time searching for the right thing, this might not be time afforded to all start-ups. The only thing I wanted more of was legal advice on how to protect my idea due to how IP heavy it is.” - SME

Here it was suggested that a complete and up-to-date map of internal programmes that already exist, with details about what support each could offer could be an opportunity help SMEs get to a stronger position, faster.

Many suggested that their **key to success lay in working closely with others to get expert advice and guidance to overcome barriers**. Having a clinical friend to support with ideas and products focused in health came across as really valuable to SMEs, who went on to suggest that a coaching or mentor programme could be a fantastic way to support businesses in the region. We heard that people aren't necessarily looking for programmes, but instead they want key people who can share their expertise and give guidance to businesses to help with the direction of travel in a complex landscape. There is an opportunity here for Civic Data Coop to harness this thinking as a door opener in the region, connecting the businesses with the experts.

“There is not enough opportunity for clinicians or care givers to use their lived experience to found a business. Often these people are full of great ideas. There needs to be more links between the start-up ecosystem and healthcare in general”
- SME

We also heard that SMEs are aware that clinicians and care givers are full of great ideas for innovation, but perhaps do not consider entrepreneurship as an option when they are time poor and unsure of where to start in a space in familiar to them. With some structure here there is a real opportunity to add value to the system, bringing people into the conversation who may be full of ideas and considerations of what needs to be improved to make a real difference to people’s lives, and helping them navigate the space to collaborate with businesses that have the skills to bring an idea to life.

6.3.3 Insights

We heard that SMEs felt that **products being led by people with lived experience often did better in the innovation space**, with people who are passionate and experienced in what they do leading the field in change and innovation. Some felt that with some niche expertise given to their solution, SMEs could go on to be more successful at winning contracts and bringing a product to market.

An interviewee also spoke about how they **struggled to recruit staff with tech skills to their team as they began to grow in size**, raising questions about whether there is a shortage of qualified potential applicants in the region to recruit into developing teams.

These insights tell us that we need the right people around the table at every stage, when we are thinking about solution generation, but also as businesses begin to

grow, we need to ensure there are skills available to support the development of an idea, whether as a full-time role, or via an expert in the sector who can advise on best practice.

SMEs spoke loudly about not understanding or prioritising impact. Often, it is disregarded early on and if or when they do stumble across it, they struggle to understand where to start and can be put off by the expense. We were told that access to Google analytics is expensive for start ups, where **SMEs wanted to invest for impact measuring and management and felt out of reach for some projects that needed to evidence their reach online.**

Data and the impact on Privacy was skirted around in conversations, again an area which felt intimidating for SMEs. An example shared was from a mental health support app. The app had feedback from their users that adverts for mental health support would appear on their devices after they had accessed the app, putting them off further engagement, as **algorithms that were difficult to break would affect the privacy their customers really needed.**

Technology and the provision of online services, dashboards, analytics and algorithms sits behind much of the innovation in this space. There is an gap in the system for SMEs to have better skills to capitalise and tailor better intelligence in this space.

6.3.4 Needs

Commonly many participants from the SME community spoke about **needing expert advice and better relationships with influential people in the public sector.**

Participants spoke about the un-met need for facilitated introduction to people working within the system who face viable problems. In the current landscape it is really difficult to start these relationships. It was acknowledged people working in the public sector are time-poor but it is essential for these relationships to be built for ideas to have a better chance of finding solutions to real life problems.

In contrast, we also heard that some advice currently received through the system is not expert enough, and that when an idea is niche it is difficult to get to the level of expertise required to progress an idea.

“Current business support landscape in LCR is too disjointed. There are lots of things happening, but too many organisations offering the same thing, and too many good ideas slipping through the net due to the lack of sign-posting for good quality business support” - SME

SMEs spoke about scaling up of idea with the support from clinicians specifically. Some interviewees has experienced issues in the past when clinicians needed a a higher level of digital confidence to ensure ideas can be progressed. This speaks to the earlier points raised by supporting organisations of the culture withing public sectors where adopting new methods is seen as high risk.

Alongside the need for clinical support for health problems, we also heard that SMEs have struggled to get legal advice for IP protection, good financial planning support and better relationships with procurement so that business models can be more robust.

"Although I had contact with the [SME Support Org], I had more success travelling to London to find funding for my idea" - SME

If these areas of support could be improved, SMEs spoke about the need to fail faster, to overcome and evolve quicker.

6.3.5 Themes

There were several developing themes that started to emerge from our conversations with businesses and entrepreneurs, but also some conflicting points depending on the maturity of the business or idea and the area their product was developed for.

Some businesses are set up alongside full-time job or the developer is often already working, this can make ideas risky as the **developer is time poor or pursuing their idea as a passion project, which is a high-risk approach**. On the contrary those **businesses that are more developed want better advice on scaling up, rather than innovation**.

"One of the biggest barriers to founding a tech business is the fact that you either have to do it around your current job, which means you won't get it done very quickly and it's likely you will lose momentum, or that you give up your job altogether, hoping things will work out" - SME

Others were quick to acknowledge that **SMEs could feel like they were stuck in a cycle of creating solutions to non-urgent problems and needed to get closer to the root of health and social civic issues** rather than top level summary of health issues. This acknowledgement speaks clearly to the same issue we heard raised multiple times by providers, and shows a real appetite from entrepreneurs to listen to leaders

in the sector, so they can understand the real need for innovation in health and social services.

Here businesses also felt they would benefit from **better access to public health data to accelerate development**, believing that access to more data would help to articulate and evidence the problem and solution. Often these businesses shared they hoped the Civic Data Coop could make this a priority as they begin to establish themselves in the region.

6.3.5 System Challenges

Specifically in terms of data access all SMEs who engaged with our interviews shared that improved quality or access to data could help their organisations grow in some way. We repeatedly heard that access to GP data could be empowering, as it is understood to be a rich source of valuable information that paints a detailed picture of our communities and the complexities within them

To create their own rich data set, one SME spoke about designing and conducting their own surveys directed at feeding into their solution generation, but these were considered to be too intrusive for users.

“When developing our mental health support app, there was no access to NHS and the CCG felt like a closed shop. We had to formulate our own user surveys, so they were more intrusive than they needed to be” - SME

We also heard from one interviewee that they struggled to access business support through the system because of the governance of their organisation. Set up as a charity, they found that actually this meant they were exempt from various packages of business support. We can therefore understand that the organisational governance space can be complex, and businesses need considered options at the right time, to ensure they aren't punished by the system at later stage, cutting off access to valuable support.

“We didn't realise when we set up with good intentions as a charity that this would make us largely exempt from business support. Some guidance around this at the start would have saved us a lot of heartache” - SME

Repeatedly concerns were echoed across various conversations about ideas getting crushed once they reached legal or procurement public sector teams, showing a real divide between the demand for ideas and what continues to be presented to commissioning. If SMEs could better understand how teams sitting in our providers think, and how they need to present to and interact with teams such as commissioning, procurement and legal they would be more likely to see ideas succeed. We know that this must be considered in our programme design to allow SMEs an opportunity to build stronger solutions that are considered and concise, in the opinion of these internal system teams.

DRAFT

7. OVERLAP DISCUSSION

Over the course of 75+ conversations held in our research phase, we heard many different viewpoints on the successes and failures of the current system. Taking a bird's eye view of all the points raised, there were strong messages that came through from the community as well as some conflicting views on how successfully SMEs are able to work in health and social care environments. In order to design the Design Thinking for Health programme we now need to consider all these angles to develop something of value in Liverpool City Region to provide better opportunities to tackle knotty problems and enable SMEs to get access to the support they need the most.

During our research phase it quickly became apparent that the health sector is currently better positioned than that of local authority and social care providers, so our line of enquiry pivoted early on accommodate this. This was measured against our understanding of the money that is currently flowing into health and the lack there of in social care. This became our focus as an area of neglect that was spoken about frequently through our conversations with leaders in the public sector.

With energy and cash being streamlined into the health space, we were left wondering what needs to happen to enable more innovation in social care. When speaking to Local Authorities we heard that culture can be a barrier to change, but overall sector leaders acknowledged that there needs to be more proactive innovation and conversations in the non-health space.

We know that a lot of the thinking in this space is short term, often resulting in action that is short lived and not embedded into a siloed and complex system to improve services across the board over time. There is a politically driven spend in public services, where ideas get stuck in the rabbit wheel and struggle to make it past procurement and legal, where ideas get spat out with little to no support with how to be more successful next time. As a programme Design Thinking for Health will need to be given time to mature and pivot to the needs of all stakeholders in the system. There is a need for medium-longer term thinking on civic exemplar projects that isn't being met where there is a clear opportunity for SMEs to be given direction from the system, so that they can fail faster and succeed better.

The public sector landscape is intricate and complex, with no linear access to experts and departments. All stakeholders struggle to navigate this, whether it's improving communication between teams, or nurturing relationships between SMEs and experts in the field. People are not working together to find the best solution to problems, and there is a hunger from SMEs to be better connected to the intelligence from day one, facilitated by stronger relationships with a desire for an organisation such as Civic Data Coop to help entrepreneurs navigate and distil this

data for more efficient horizon scanning, and clearer strategic aims needed for all stakeholders.

Currently data is an afterthought for SMEs, and it became clear that the skill level when thinking about data was varied, with some not really knowing what they wanted or needed from the system. Many spoke about the desire to have better access to GP data, as the richest source of information that is likely to exist on our communities, but what was not clear was if this was available that SMEs would have the skill to analyse and use the information effectively. In conjunction with this, the commissioning culture within services also doesn't always need evidence of data to win contracts, which can be awarded in block, with little opportunity for SMEs to get a foot in the door.

As conversations around data can often feel overwhelming to many of the stakeholders there could be an opportunity here for an educational piece around data and its use, not just for the general public, to bring them into to conversation, but also for businesses, entrepreneurs and public sector teams.

We heard mixed reviews on SME support that is currently available in LCR, with vast variation on perspectives. Some spoke about a heavy focus on scaling up businesses, whereas others felt that support was not directed at all in this space. On reflection we wondered if this links back to the discussions we had with sector leaders who spoke about SMEs not understanding the most pressing problems. Perhaps this point about scaling up really reflects the low appetite from public sector to adopt solutions to problems with a smaller potential for impact.

Overwhelmingly health and social care provider interviewees spoke about a need for the sector to present the problems to the fixers. Time and time again interviewees said that SMEs do not really understand the most important issues faced by providers, and they would do better to be involved in these dialogues. If the sector could frame the problems better, we would see better demand led innovation and turn the current pattern up stream where solutions are currently being led by fixers and falling flat when they pitch to industry leaders that invest and commission products and services.

Some SMEs also spoke about a desire for better connections and introduction to peers, not always expertise, although others thought there was a greater need for more specific expertise support. This programme has an opportunity to connect all stakeholders together into a more robust framework for support and connections between providers, people and data to really get under the skin of the problems our region is facing.

8. CONCLUSION

As a response to the problems, we discussed across all stakeholders we will be designing an event to bring to the surface some of these issues and present opportunities for SMEs to engage better with providers, with the ambition to give financial and expert advice to selected solutions in the region.

Our approach to this has its foundations in the insights we gathered from supporting organisations and service providers. We therefore want to change the trend of SMEs throwing solutions to providers who cannot accommodate their ideas, instead allowing providers to pitch ideas to SMEs and have a wider conversation around some of the challenges and opportunities with the right people in the room.

8.1 Designing the Event – The 3 Problems

From this work, we heard a number of headline problems where there felt there was an opportunity for the Civic Data Coop to make a real difference in supporting SMEs develop a solution to pitch to real people who are experts in their fields. We want to zoom in on 3 succinct problems with great potential to allow choice, but also keep focus where we have engaged participants from the sector.

Initially we scaled down all of the problems we heard providers talk about to 9 strong ideas, ready to pitch these to Civic Data Coop, so we could tie in their business development with the mobilisation of supporting SMEs better to develop solutions to these problems.

The 9 scaled down 'wicked' problems are:

1. Growing number of children going into residential care.
Pitch: How do we identify earlier and support to prevent admissions to residential care?
2. Telehealth/telecare solutions
Pitch: Local Authorities are shifting from analogue to digital solutions and know their systems and applications are behind the curve. How can we best support them to become digitally enabled?
3. Communication across internal teams
Pitch: How do we get internal depts talking to each other e.g., Benefits/missed payments triggering help? We need to know we are working with the right families (In this instance the problem came from Early Help, but we could apply this question to various workstreams)?

4. Co-production in statutory services
Pitch: How do we engage service users better with the programmes they participate in, instead of prescribing programmes that don't inspire long term positive change? As examples:
 - a. DV 'forced' into engaging with a programme. Often programmes are not implemented at the right time or there is no desire to be participate. Social workers push to this as evidence 'help' and reduce risk. Referral is quick and it comes off their to do list. This leads to big waiting lists for courses people do not want to go to, so they either don't attend at all or stop after first/second session.... leads to 'you're not committed to protecting your child if you don't engage'.
 - b. How do we increase choice of help e.g., going for a swim alongside making those conversations as easy for Social workers and give the ability to evidence for when things go wrong or OFSTED come to inspect? Need to increase choice and make that support route as easy as a referral into a programme
 - c. Getting parents involved in SEN
5. Poor educational outcomes
Pitch: How do we support our schools and pupils better?
 - a. Some of the problem is centred around poor school leadership and teaching. Some is the lack of value we are placing on education, decline in respect.
 - b. We could make progress by embedding community support into schools
 - c. Intergenerational poor experiences of education, can we change the pattern and messaging?
6. Improving our environments
Pitch: How do we improve the environments in our region, when they have a lasting impact on population health?
 - a. Litter picking- how can we play a bigger role in keeping our environments clean?
 - b. Environment bigger factor on health than lifestyle choices yet tech solutions focus on that. How do we get more innovation in environment?
7. Housing stock is poor
Pitch: When properties are falling into disrepair and still lived in, how can SMEs or Communities help?
8. Children presenting with asthma due to poor air quality and damp housing

Pitch: We know Alder Hey are seeing children present with severe asthma across the region, can we reduce this by intervening earlier?

9. Community mobilisation

Pitch: How can we support communities to mobilize through data and tech?

From these ideas CDC selected the 3 following most robust problems:

- **Problem 1**

Reducing childhood asthma through better environments and awareness

Presented by *Liverpool City Council*

The UK has some of the worst statistics for children affected by asthma in the world (Asthma UK, 2021), and the North West is no exception.

With rising pollution rates in one of the leading industrial areas in the country, prevalence of asthma in children is at an all time high (Asthma UK, 2021). We've seen the news and we are starting to make changes, but is that enough?

The proportion of children who attend A&E for asthma exacerbations are too high and they come from areas of poor air quality and poor housing.

"I just want him to be able to breathe"

We're already starting to use data to identify congestion hotspots in the city and using this information to improve air quality. So, why not take this thinking further and, closer to home. If we already have the data, let's start to think about how we can use it to better place future housing across the LCR for healthier generations to come.

- **Problem 2**

Increasing family support to stop children entering care

Presented by *Wirral Council*

Providing early help support and intervention is vital to stop children entering the care system when they are older. We can see there is a continual increase in children going into residential care. How can we identify families who are struggling earlier and support them better?

"I feel like her life story is written... it's not even started"

It may seem like a relatively simple ask, but understanding high-risk areas and practically implementing the early-help support that is needed, can be challenging in it's own right.

There are a multitude of factors that can increase risk to a child's wellbeing including: lack of a strong support network for the family, poor social and emotional skills, little community services and no/minimal income and beneficiary support.

That's a lot of areas to look at to be proactive and prevent, rather than acting when it's too late.

By working closely with organisations that support through early-help, we want to find ways to identify areas for risk in a more timely way. If we do it right, this will create a better outcome for both the child and family.

- **Problem 3**

Making digital feel doable in local authority social care teams

Presented by *Halton Borough Council*

In the 21st century, digital systems need to be at heart of our public services, but we know this can be a mountain to climb. They can be scary, overwhelming and more often than not, completely confusing. This can put ideas around 'digital' on the back foot from the outset.

The Civic Data Cooperative understands the value data holds and the potential it has to make a real difference to people's lives. But before organisations can get comfortable with the data, they need to get comfortable with digital.

It's no secret that those who work in social care have some of the most demanding roles out there. The COVID-19 pandemic has not only heightened his pressure, but raised awareness across the general public of the challenges of these teams. Understandably this pressure (particularly at present) doesn't always leave the time or space to think of new and/or more efficient ways of digitising their day to day.

That being said, implementing improved digital processes (in the ways we record, share and communicate across social work) can have huge advantages, as well as mitigating risk. Our Local Authorities want to be digitally enabled but are struggling with where to start and don't have the capability to progress. So, how can we help our Local Authorities to be digitally able?

“We want to move into the digital world but it feels massive and we don't know where to start”

But before we jump in with a solution, let's talk about the issues arising across social care and how we can make introducing digital thinking more 'doable' for those who are already doing an amazing job.

8.2 Designing the Event – What’s your problem?

Pulling insights together has helped us identify what the key drivers behind the launch event need to be. After engaging with multiple stakeholders, we know our focus must be to bring together businesses and the voluntary sector with the people who’ve studied, or have been working within these problems, we can explore deeper and develop more fit-for-purpose solutions together.

Aims of event:

- Create meaningful connections between SMEs and Local Authorities or mentors
- Better understand the 3 big problems
- Curate ‘teams’ who want to work together to progress the problem to idea
- ‘Soft’ launch Civic Data Coop as an organisation in Liverpool City Region
- Gather insights to shape the functions of Civic Data Coop and test functionality

(right people + right questions) x right data = product and service design that works

Leaders in the public sector have highlighted to us their stickiest issues, and they have offered their time and expertise to work through them with us on the day. This will give us the opportunity to take the time to ask the big questions of those in the know, whether that’s about opportunities that come from those problems or the barriers they and you are facing (whether that’s adoption, integration, or growth).

It's clear that LCR is not short on creativity, but often the problems solutions are designed to address are misunderstood. For ideas to be adopted, businesses and the voluntary sector need to start by developing their knowledge and awareness of the environments, culture and sector intricacies, that make these problems so difficult to solve.

We understand that CDC need to be purposeful about the format of the event, learning from the feedback we have heard from SMEs about tired delivery methods, that don’t drive connections and progress. We plan to design the event to be different from the usual format, making sure it’s about creativity in public service products and services but we've listened to what innovators (businesses and the voluntary sector) and the public sector have told us. Therefore, we understand the format must shift away from being a brainstorm, or traditional hackathon. Instead of coming up with ideas straight away, we want delegates to spend some time getting deeper under the skin of the problems we will raise.

This programme will therefore be made up of two stages - the event, and after the event. It will be designed to focus specifically on understanding, before giving

participants the tools and space to think creatively about product and service opportunities. For that reason the launch event is problem orientated only.

The **purpose** of the launch event will be to more clearly and tightly define the problems that ‘innovators’ are being asked to solve.

Before the event takes place we want attendees to feel informed about why attending will benefit them. We will share the problems with delegates, including the stories behind the problems, from the perspective of sector leaders who are dealing with them daily, giving SMEs and supporting organisations the change to have a ‘peak behind the curtain’ before the show begins.

We heard that meaningful data needs to be more readily available for innovators, so we want to bring together a set of resources to help to frame our three big problems well. These will bring together a range of materials including case studies, reports, academic papers, online resources and data sets. We recognise that part of the event should then address what is missing from this information and what else SMEs and entrepreneurs need to be well informed enough to start thinking about solutions.

We want stakeholders to build meaningful connections with others working hard in this space. If we can set up the stakeholders to interact meaningfully with experts in the region we can help connections to be built and open doors for SMEs, who in turn can progress faster through the system to harbour, inform and brand an idea so it is public service ready.

Beyond the event

After we have held the event and better understand the 3 big problems, we will invite SMEs with interest and ideas around our 3 big problems to be part of the second phase of the programme. This phase will offer grants of up to £20k alongside connections to a wealth of experts and educational tools to support the problem thinking to transition into solution generation. The themes generated from the insights will ground how we design and curate the expert team who will support the SMEs in the development of their ideas.

We hope that this will deepen innovation routes by seeding viable ideas, backed with valuable, digestible real data and connections across the community from all stakeholders to are passionate about finding the best solutions for our citizens.

8.3 Development of the Civic Data Coop Organisation

This report also set out to inform the development of Civic Data Coop as it establishes itself in the city region. All of the participants we spoke to when conducting the research for this report were excited about the idea of Civic Data Coop and were keen to interact with the organisation as it proves itself in the region. The narrative around the expectation of what CDC show be, however, did vary across our conversations with stakeholders, from a provider and SME perspective, so it is clear that Civic Data Coop need to articulate their position well with businesses in the region, to meet or manage expectations.

What we have learnt from these conversations is that it is important that CDC considers its purpose as the following:

- **A door opener**

There is a real opportunity through the launch event and through further touch points in the system for CDC to help build stronger bridges between providers, SMEs and the people in the region with great ideas. The stakeholders have asked for more meaningful connections to programmes and expertise, as well as a more in depth understanding of the system priorities to improve the way conversations happen across the landscape.

If CDC can begin to connect the right people together, and help stakeholders understand which programme of support is most needed for them at their stage of development, the hope is that SMEs ideas will fail faster, become stronger and succeed better.

- **Led by people, not policy**

We heard from our experts that solutions to problems need to be embedded in the communities or our region if we want to see real change for the better. Over time, this could create meaningful change to the way that our providers commission services, putting commissioners more in the heart of the organisation, with the vision to understand how new innovative solutions, that offer digital and data driven alternatives to traditional service delivery methods.

Alongside this, we know that there is a challenge to bring the public along on this journey, involving them in the conversation and giving them the pedestal to have a voice in what the solutions must be. Without the support of citizens, we know we will face barriers at the point of delivery, if understanding and trust has not been built from the start.

- **A place where accurate data sets can be linked and easily used**

We now know that stakeholders struggle to access the data they need to inform and manage services in all parts of the system. There is a real appetite to improve the quality of this data, and create a place where valid, live, usable data sets are available to extract, so that solutions can be better informed by evidence.

The majority of stakeholders spoke hopefully about the gap CDC could fill providing a platform or dashboard for innovators to access, which would spit out valuable, detailed resources. The data would need to really get to the root cause of the problems, linking sets together, in order for it to be valuable for SMEs and providers alike. Currently this doesn't exist anywhere in the system.

We recommend that as part of the launch event data is made available to frame the 3 big problems better, but also recognise that there needs to be a discussion around what else is needed to help support the stakeholders in their solution design.

DRAFT

9. APPENDIX

	Number of interviews conducted
Local Authority	19
Support Organisations	30
SMEs	26

DRAFT